

Twin on a chip brains for monitoring individual sleep habits

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This deliverable is designed to support the objective of WP 7 – Communication, Outreach and Dissemination strategy and Innovation Potential. Indeed, within the frame of WP7 and in particular the task T7.2, and according to that declared in the Grant Agreement – Description of Action, Section 2, the definition of the project identity and of the website structure are needed to support all dissemination, communication, outreach and exploitation activities of the project.

In this deliverable, the actions necessary for the creation of the project identity, including NAP logo, and the media, e.g., website and social accounts, are detailed.

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1. Introduction

NAP aims at assessing the ability of the next generation of biohybrid in vitro brains to serve as downscaled and personalised model of sleep, and to predict sleep-related early warning signs of Parkinson's Disease.

Implementing an appealing, eye-catching, well-focused, pleasant, intuitive to use and accessible across devices and browsers website is one of the first key steps in any research project, so as to adequately disseminate its main objectives to get attention from the desired public. Creating the project virtual identity, as well as complementing the basic project website with additional presence in the social networks is also fundamental for supporting the overall communication and dissemination strategy with very dynamic capabilities, especially attractive to the younger international public.

The Deliverable 7.1 is designed to support the objective of WP7 – Dissemination, Outreach, Communication and Exploitation strategy and Innovation Potential. More specifically, it addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the NAP graphical identity, i.e., a project logo and its associated colours. The colour scheme and logo will accompany the project during its whole life, as a harmonized and consistent way of transmitting the project image to the public. This will increase all partners' abilities to communicate the project mission, objectives and main achievements. On the other hand, the project website, hosted under the URL: www.horizoneic-nap.eu, will act as one stop shop of NAP; it contains several sections, one each dedicated to a specific set of information. The objective is to keep the most updated information about the project progresses, always available for all our stakeholders.

This Deliverable aims at describing such visual elements of the project and how to use them consistently across all media and communications, as well as at providing all the Beneficiaries with guidelines for using the NAP identity, in a harmonised and clear manner.

The items presented in this deliverable form a basis for all further visuals of the project and of the future Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.2, M6).

2. NAP identity

The visual identity for NAP has been developed during the very beginning of the project, to ensure a clear, consistent, and recognizable brand for all communications, and to underline the project's philosophy and objectives.

2.1 Logo

NAP logo is shown in Figure 1. It has been designed by UNIPI and represents the ideas behind the NAP project in a sort of 'graphical abstract'.

Indeed, the colours chosen, i.e., hexadecimal colour codes #253761 and #F4B63F, recall day and night, and so the sleep/wake cycles. This is also highlighted by the sun and the moon. The other elements presented, i.e., the neuron and the electrodes, are introduced for presenting in a nutshell the NAP envisioned technology: a biohybrid *in vitro* 3D constructs, with electrodes for monitoring neuron electrophysiological activity.

Figure 1 NAP logo

The logo must appear in all the official communications and may not be modified in any way. It is available in multiple formats for both print and website use (i.e., SVG format for high quality printing, PNG for web use with transparency and JPEG for simple web use) to all the Consortium members through the shared folder set up by the Project Coordinator.

3. NAP stakeholders

For maximizing NAP impact and thus better designing the website and identifying the suitable social media channels, we firstly identified the potential stakeholders of our project. For each of them, based on their characteristics we have already identified tailored key messages, with the aim of defining the best modes to approach them, as described in the Grant Agreement – Description of Action, and reported in Table 1.

Table 1. NAP stakeholders and target key messages.

NAP stakeholders	Target key messages
Scientific Community and Organizations	NAP breakthroughs and, in turn, <i>NAP Proof of Principle</i> can give a key contribution to study individual sleep pathophysiology NAP strategy can be customized for quantitatively evaluating the (patho)physiological relevance of different <i>in vitro</i> constructs

	<i>NAP envisioned technology</i> will identify early-stage PD patients that could be interested in adhering as volunteers to test new therapies
Healthcare operators	<i>The NAP envisioned technology</i> has the potential to predate PD diagnosis, thus decreasing the healthcare costs and simplify aged care.
Investors, other financial actors	<i>NAP envisioned technology</i> for predating PD can create real economic value, generating new business in our aging society
Biotech/Pharma Industry	The innovation potential of the <i>NAP Proof of Principle</i> and <i>envisioned technology</i> can provide a new tool for drug testing and neurotoxicity
Citizen groups (e.g., Night workers, Schools, Patients associations)	<i>NAP Proof of Principle</i> and breakthroughs give tangible of the effects of sleep deprivation and disorders on individual brains, raising awareness on the role of prevention and of the early detection of neuropathies <i>NAP envisioned technology</i> will give the opportunity to routinely screen ourselves and our relatives for predating PD diagnosis
Space Agencies	<i>NAP envisioned technology</i> will give the opportunity to routinely screen astronauts' sleep and study sleep/wake cycles in weightless environment
Clinicians	The <i>NAP envisioned technology</i> has an important clinical potential, e.g., as a support for early ND diagnosis
Policy Makers, Public Authorities	Foster discussion and debate about the potential positive effects of NAP on economy and society, and about the need to strength the e-health and the need to identify new protocols for its managing.
Journalists	NAP project has a strong scientific, technological, and social component on hot topics such as sleep and PD, which attract the public opinion
General Audience	<i>NAP Proof of Principle</i> funded by EU improve citizen lives since it give tangible insights on the effects of sleep deprivation and disorders

4. Social Media identity

Social networks play an important role in getting the public interested in NAP activities and allowing participation and interaction. For spreading information to interested users via the social web, we set up five different media channels (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook Meta, Instagram and YouTube). The social accounts have been chosen for maximizing NAP visibility to different stakeholders via short bite-sized messages suitable for this type of media.

4.1 Twitter

Twitter remains one of the key sources for current affairs in modern society. Discover what people are talking about all over the world to reach new and large audiences. Keeping an eye out for relevant topics and hashtags related to NAP and with the right content and timing, the project could reach thousands of followers. For this reason, UNIPI has created a Twitter account under @NAP_HORIZONEIC (https://twitter.com/NAP_HORIZONEIC)

Through relevant and popular hashtags, the consortium can find people who may be interested in NAP project and drive them to follow the project across all our social media accounts, thus increasing the pool of people interested in our activities. Relevant tweets from other accounts focused on sleep, 3Rs, *in vitro* models, neuroscience and electrophysiology will be retweeted.

Currently, the Twitter account has amassed 12 followers, earned over 50 interactions since its inception on March 1st, 2023.

A screenshot of the Twitter NAP homepage is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 NAP Twitter homepage

4.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn mission is to 'connect the world's professionals to make them more productive and successful' As such, it is an ideal platform to increase NAP presence online, in the view of maximizing the innovation potential of its outcomes. Thanks to LinkedIn, EU funded projects could network with an increasing number of interesting contacts. Project LinkedIn account is: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/horizon-eic-nap-32a256268/>.

Using the different personal and group features in LinkedIn, the project and the people involving in NAP can all improve their visibility. Just as other social networks do, LinkedIn has a social sharing button that enables the consortium to share content in its status updates (which are visible on the homepage) and in LinkedIn Groups (communities). Relevant posts from other accounts focused on sleep, 3Rs, in vitro models, neuroscience and electrophysiology will be reposted.

Currently, the LinkedIn account has amassed 36 followers, with 81 users visiting the profile, and earned over 128 impressions since its inception on March 1st 2023.

A screenshot of the LinkedIn NAP homepage is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 NAP LinkedIn homepage

4.3 Facebook Meta

Meta mission is to 'give people the capacity to form communities and bring the globe closer together'. To this end, Meta will be used to announce NAP publications, news and events, so that they can be available to a larger public. Relevant posts from other accounts focused on sleep, 3Rs, in vitro models, neuroscience and electrophysiology will be re-posted. Audio-visual contents will be regularly posted. Project Facebook Meta page is: <https://www.facebook.com/NAPHORIZONEIC>.

Currently, the Facebook Meta account has amassed 69 likes and 78 followers, earned over 250 impressions since its inception on March 1st 2023.

A screenshot of the Meta NAP homepage is given in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Meta NAP homepage

4.4 Instagram

Instagram mission statement revolves around creating visual impressions that leave its users with long-standing memories. Nowadays, Instagram has a strong following among teens and young adults. To this end, NAP will broaden its community including younger people creating the @nap_horizoneic account (https://www.instagram.com/nap_horizoneic).

Figure 5 NAP Instagram homepage

Since it is a visual platform, we will create contents that make people more aware of the activities carried out in the labs. We will routinely group the most relevant stories under different Instagram Stories Highlights, to let the users easily track all our activities.

Currently, the Instagram account has amassed 57 followers, earned over 100 impressions since its inception on March 1st, 2023.

4.5 YouTube

YouTube is a video-sharing website that allows people to upload, watch and share videos. The platform serves as a forum for people to inform, inspire and engage with others. NAP YouTube channel is https://www.youtube.com/@NAP_HORIZONEIC.

Figure 6 NAP YouTube homepage

We have already used the NAP YouTube channel for streaming the first part of the Kick-off meeting, held in Pisa on 22nd-23rd, March 2023. The first intervention by the Project Coordinator, detailing NAP background, objectives, breakthrough, and long-term impacts is still available.

5. Website

The main aim of the NAP project website is to inform our stakeholders of the background and status of our activities and to give insights into the research and publications.

The main challenge in designing a broad-spectrum communication platform is the diversity of potential audience groups, each of whom has different levels of understanding and experience, resulting in different expectations and familiarity with a website describing such a complex and interdisciplinary project. As such, given the huge heterogeneity of the stakeholders (Table 1), in designing the website, we tried to achieve a trade-off between technicalisms and accessibility of the information.

The website is accessible at <https://www.horizoneic-nap.eu>. For strengthening NAP visual identity, the website template has been built with the same hexadecimal colour code used for the logo.

The WP7 leader is responsible to ensure that the sections are up to date with the latest news and information. The NAP Consortium members promptly inform the WP7 leader for updating their sections and for asking for adding news and communications.

At the time of the first release, March 15th, 2023, the website is available in English. However, some of the content will be presented in other languages, e.g., press releases from national media.

Google analytics will be used to track the number of visits and to analyse trends in the behaviours of visitors to the project's website. This monitoring will be carried out throughout the project. Useful insights may be obtained, including how long visitors remain on the website, how many pages of the website visitors' views and which content was most popular. The content and structure of the website may then be tailored to satisfy the interests of the website visitors, thus attracting additional traffic.

5.1 Hosting and maintenance

The site has been created by UNIFI using *googlesite* and is hosted by *register.it* (Italy). It is available for monitor, tablet and phone screens.

5.2 Site structure

The homepage is the normal point of entry for first time site visitors. It is structured in a way that, within the small area of the screen that the visitor sees when the site first loads, he/she has the key message in succinct and visually impactful way.

The homepage contains:

1. A menu bar
2. NAP logo
3. NAP main objective
4. A sketch with the NAP Proof of Concept and envisioned technology
5. NAP impacts
6. A section for subscribing to the NAP newsletter;
7. A footer with the social links and the EU grant acknowledgment information

In addition to providing a traditional navigation menu to assist the usability, we have taken it a step further in making the navigation always appear at the top of the screen when viewed on a desktop/laptop computer. This 'sticky' menu provides a grounding anchor for the site visitor. This form of navigation enables a user to move from one section of the site to another with minimal click-throughs to achieve it.

The homepage is shown in Figure 7.

Sleep is an essential part of everyday life, and its disturbances affect people emotional and cognitive well-being. Sleep disturbances are early warning signs of Parkinson's Disease, predicted to rise from 40 to 135 Mln worldwide in 30 years

Twin on a chip brains for monitoring individual sleep habits

NAP makes real the study of individual sleep pathophysiology through a new science-to-technology paradigm merging in vitro modelling, allometric scaling, signal processing and micromanufacturing

NAP Proof of Principle

The cyborganoïds, the first bihybrid enabling technology for long-term monitoring of sleep and wake states *in vitro*, identifying individual sleep habits, studying sleep deprivation and detecting its anomalies predicting Parkinson's Disease.

NAP envisioned technology

Innovative *twin-on-a-chip* for predictive medicine, exploiting in a totally new and unexplored way *in vitro* biotechnologies for routinely monitoring our sleep health and being promptly warned about alterations due to sleep deprivation or sleep-related disorders.

NAP impacts

NAP is expected to make significant transformative effects in science, society, economy and regulation

BIOMEDICAL RESEARCH

The cyborganoïds represent the next generation of *in vitro* models of a person's brain; beyond the project aims, the cyborganoïds can be customized to other organ models that can benefit from electrical stimulation or recording, e.g., gut and heart models, providing unexplored read-out. We will deliver a novel tool enabling the extrapolation of biological parameters from *in vitro* to the human context.

SOCIETY

NAP outcomes will represent a unique tool for predictive personalised medicine, helping prelate PD (and other neuropathies) diagnosis in females and males, a global challenge in our getting older society. The early diagnosis will help people to plan ahead for their care, financial and legal matters.

ECONOMY

NAP's long-term exploitation of the cyborganoïds will support health operators to provide timely and thus more effective treatments and advice regarding care, that will scale back healthcare costs. The cyborganoïds will give fresh impetus to pharmaceutical research and enterprise, boosting growth, competitiveness and attractiveness of EU as a leading voice for tackling prompt PD diagnosis and sleep deprivation.

POLICY MAKERS

The emphasis on the consequences on sleep deprivation will promote the implementation of new policies to properly regulate working hours and schedules, improve access to ambulatory in-home diagnostic testing and promote national and local public health campaigns focusing on the importance of sleep, also as part of a national sleep strategy. Because sleep health is unevenly distributed across the population, NAP is a necessary step toward health equity.

Figure 7 The homepage of the NAP website

5.2.1 The Project

'The Project' section, accessible through the menu, contains information about the project objectives and breakthroughs, along with a graphical abstract of the NAP methodology in a nutshell and of the 'toolkit' for achieving our objectives.

This Section is shown in Figure 8.

NAP breakthroughs

- The first model enabling the study of individual sleep habits
- The cyborganoïd: the next generation of models of the human brain.
- A new procedure mimicking personalized sleep
- A new unified way to study sleep, from cells to humans
- A new tool for predicting Parkinson's Disease.

NAP in a nutshell

- NAP breakthroughs and specific objectives are achieved through:
- the **collaborative development** (e.g., *cyborganoïd*)
 - the application of **common experimental approaches** (e.g., scaling-based drug stimulation for *in vitro* functional/structural characterization, and the use of allometry for defining sleep in cells and humans)
 - the use of **complementary technologies** (e.g., electrophysiology and calcium imaging)
 - the **comparison of observations across groups** (from *in vitro* constructs up to humans, accounting sex).

Figure 8 'The Project' section of the NAP website

The consortium

In 'The Consortium' section, the Beneficiaries of the grant are listed; more specifically, the institutions involved, their locations and their logos are visualised.

For each Beneficiary, a dedicated page is created, storing information about the institution, along with a picture and short bio of the people involved in NAP research, financial and administrative activities. These pages are also accessible through the pop-up menu appearing while clicking on 'The Consortium' in the menu bar.

This Section is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 'The Consortium' Section of the NAP website

The Boards

'The Boards' section contains information about the three boards supporting NAP research and innovation:

1. Board of the Ethical Management
2. Legal and Ethical Board
3. Innovation Potential Board

More specifically, the boards' duties and the contacts of the members of each board are listed.

This Section is shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 'The Boards' Section of the NAP website

The resources

'The resources' section is designed as a pop-up menu with the following categories, each of them designed for specific target groups:

1. Presentations and Publications
2. Public deliverables
3. Press kit
4. Photo and Video Gallery

Since NAP fully adheres to EU Open Science principles for publications and data, in the first two subsections, we will store all the publications, presentations to conferences and deliverables labelled as 'PUBLIC' in the Grant Agreement.

In the 'Press kit' subsection, we will collect the pdf of the brochure, the newsletters (to be described in Deliverable 7.2 – Communication and Dissemination plan) and any other promotional materials providing information about NAP, uploaded for the media and promotional use.

Finally, in the 'Photo and Video Gallery' subsection, we will store the pictures of the events we will participate, as well as videos produced for NAP Dissemination/Communication, that will be also uploaded in the NAP YouTube channel.

'The resources' Section is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 'The resources' Section of the NAP website

News

In 'The News' section, we will upload all the interviews and the press articles and TV shows talking about NAP activities (with external link for watching or reading the news), as well as information about the events we will participate or organize.

This Section is shown in Figure 12.

NAP at Radio24

Listen to the podcast on Smart City, by Maurizio Melis [here](#)

NAP at TG Toscana and TG Leonardo

Talking about NAP at two Scientific Italian TV news. See the interview [here](#).

NAP on LeScienze!

Read the interview [here](#)

NAP on Ansa

Read the interview [here](#)

NAP on wired

Read the interview [here](#)

NAP on 30Science

Read the interview [here](#)

NAP on AnsaBrasil

Read the interview [here](#)

NAP at SkyTG24

Read the interview [here](#)

Figure 12 'The News' Section on NAP website

6. Conclusions

This deliverable has outlined the planned approach and some early-stage activities that have been taken to create and strengthen the NAP identity. Specifically, three core components of the Dissemination, Communication, Outreach and Exploitation Work-Package have been taken:

1. NAP logo
2. NAP social media accounts
3. NAP website

It has outlined the key principles behind all three.

Deliverable 7.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan at M6 will go into more details about the dissemination and communication strategy, exploiting the logo, social media and website.

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